

EFFECT OF MINI HURDLES TRAINING ON SELECTED MOTOR COMPONENTS AMONG COLLEGE MEN PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of mini hurdles training on selected motor components among college men players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on selected motor components due to the effect of mini hurdles training among college men players. For the present study 40 men inter-collegiate players from Madurai Kamaraj University affiliated colleges, Tamilnadu were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 24 years. For the present study pre test – post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of twenty men players each and named as Group 'A' and Group 'B'. Group 'A' underwent mini hurdles training and Group 'B' has not undergone any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying ANCOVA. The level of significance was set at 0.05. The mini hurdles training had shown significant improvement in speed and agility among men players after undergoing mini hurdles training for a period of twelve weeks.

Key Words: Mini Hurdles Training, Speed, Agility & Men Players

Introduction:

Sports' training is done for improving sports performance. The sports performance, as any other type of human performance, is not the product of on single system or aspect of human personality. On the contrary, it is the product of the total personality of the sports person. The personality of a person has several dimensions e.g., physical, physiological, social and psychic. In order to improve sports performance the social and psychic capacities of the sports person also have to be improved in addition to the physical and physiological once. In other words the total personality of a sportsman has to be improved in order to improve his performance. Sports training, therefore, directly and indirectly aim at improving the personality of the sportsman. No wonder, therefore, sports training is an educational process. In hill running the athlete is using their body weight as a resistance to use against, so the driving muscles from which their leg power is derived have to work harder. Mini-hurdles are a great training tool for developing athletic speed. The aim of mini hurdling is to teach a smooth, uninterrupted running action over low obstacles. Such objects are far less intimidating to beginners than the regular hurdles used in competition. This result in the athletes running more aggressively at, over and between the hurdles, which gives them the feel for fast hurdling. The mini hurdles also encourage a fast stepping action over the hurdles, which is a desirable hurdling skill.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of mini hurdles training on selected motor components among college men players. It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on selected motor components due to the effect of mini hurdles training among college men players. For the present study 40 men inter-collegiate players from Madurai Kamaraj University affiliated colleges, Tamilnadu were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 24 years. For the present study pre test – post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of twenty men players each and named as Group 'A' and Group 'B'. Group 'A' underwent mini hurdles training and Group 'B' has not undergone any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying ANCOVA. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Table 1: Variables and Test

S.No	Variables	Tests
1	Speed	50 Meter Dash
2	Agility	Shuttle Run

Results:

The findings pertaining to analysis of covariance between experimental group and control group on selected motor components among men players for pre-post test respectively have been presented in table 2 to 3.

Table 2: Ancova between Experimental Group and Control Group on Speed of Men Players for Pre, Post and Adjusted Test

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	7.11	7.13	BG	0.004	1	0.004	0.18
			WG	0.86	38	0.02	
Post Test Mean	6.59	7.12	BG	2.77	1	2.77	165.36*
			WG	0.63	38	0.01	
Adjusted Post Mean	6.59	7.12	BG	2.71	1	2.71	165.69*
			WG	0.60	37	0.01	

* Significant at 0.05 level.

df: 1/37= 4.10

Table 2 revealed that the obtained 'F' value of 165.69 was found to be significant at 0.05 level with df 1, 37 as the tabulated value of 4.10 required to be significant at 0.05 level. The same table indicated that there was a significant difference in adjusted means of speed of college men players between experimental group and control group. The graphical representation of data has been presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparisons of Pre – Test Means Post – Test Means and Adjusted Post – Test Means for Control Group and Experimental Group In Relation To Speed

Table 3: Ancova between Experimental Group and Control Group on Agility of Men Players for Pre, Post and Adjusted Test

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	11.69	11.73	BG	0.01	1	0.01	0.49
			WG	1.05	38	0.02	
Post Test Mean	10.71	11.69	BG	9.60	1	9.60	423.65*
			WG	0.86	38	0.02	
Adjusted Post Mean	10.72	11.69	BG	9.38	1	9.38	413.04*
			WG	0.84	37	0.02	

* Significant at 0.05 level.

df: 1/37= 4.10

Table 3 revealed that the obtained 'F' value of 413.04 was found to be significant at 0.05 level with df 1, 37 as the tabulated value of 4.10 required to be significant at 0.05 level. The same table indicated that there was a significant difference in adjusted means of agility of college men players between experimental group and control group. The graphical representation of data has been presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Comparisons of Pre – Test Means Post – Test Means and Adjusted Post – Test Means for Control Group and Experimental Group in Relation to Agility

Conclusion:

- ✓ The mini hurdles training had shown significant improvement in speed among men players after undergoing mini hurdles training for a period of twelve weeks.
- ✓ The mini hurdles training had shown significant improvement in agility among men players after undergoing mini hurdles training for a period of twelve weeks.

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